

Kinetics and Mechanisms of Redox Reactions of Nitrogen(III)*

M. T. BECK, L. DOZSA and I. SZILASSY

Institute of Physical Chemistry, Kossuth Lajos University, H-4010 Debrecen, Hungary

IN its different compounds nitrogen occurs in the formal oxidation states 3- to 5+, and therefore the redox reactions of nitrogen(III)-containing compounds are very various. Depending on the conditions reduction may lead to NO, N₂O, N₂, N₃⁻, NH₂OH, N₂H₄ and NH₃ as stable final products, often via well-defined intermediates (HNO, H₂N₂O₂, H₂N₂O₃, N₂H₂). In the oxidation, the only stable product is NO₃⁻, NO₂ (N₂O₄) being formed only as an intermediate.

Many of the reactions are of practical importance in inorganic and organic preparations and separations. The reactions of arylamines with nitrous acid comprise a basic process of textile dyeing.

The biochemical significance of some of the reactions involving nitrogen(III) compounds is obvious. In many of the reduction reactions, elementary nitrogen is formed. A deeper knowledge of these reactions may provide important information on the reverse reaction : biological nitrogen fixation.

Finally, investigations on the correlations between the reactivity of nitrogen(III) and its immediate environment can contribute to the clarification of the fundamental problem of the effect of coordination on kinetic behaviour. Many recent studies of solution reactions indicate that an important role is played by various reversible equilibria prior to the redox reaction, leading to the formation of species of different reactivities. Our own studies have focused on these reversible interactions and their kinetic consequences.

Among the different forms of nitrogen(III) we have dealt with nitrous acid, nitrite ion, and complexes of nitro, nitrito and nitrosyl ligands. In these complexes, of course, the nitrogen is strongly and differ-

ently polarized and the oxidation state 3+ is only an approximate characterization. The polarization is particularly powerful in the case of the different nitrosyl compounds and nitrosyl complexes. There has long been a dispute¹ on the oxidation state of the nitrogen atom of the NO group in the nitrosylpentacyanoiron(II) complex, which served as a model compound for our studies. We believe this dispute to be based on a faulty posing of the question. However, the fact that in weakly alkaline medium the following equilibrium occurs² :

suggests an analogy between this species and the well-defined nitrocomplexes, and a comparative study evidently yields information on the effect of the immediate environment on the reactivity.

Methods

In our kinetic studies the reactions were mainly followed spectrophotometrically and gas-volumetrically. The empirical rate laws were determined from the initial rates, but the conversion curves were always calculated and in no case was there a measurable deviation between the calculated and experimentally determined concentrations below 70 per cent conversion. For the postulation of the mechanism the empirical rate laws and additional information (chemical analysis and identification of products and intermediates, mass spectrometric measurements, etc.) were considered.

Redox reactions of nitrous acid and the nitrite ion

Empirical rate laws were determined for many redox reactions of nitrite ion and nitrous acid. It appears that in a number of reactions the rate is independent of the concentration of the partner, in other cases the order of the reactant is one, while in certain reactions the order lies between zero and one.

*To be read at the Golden Jubilee Conference of the Indian Chemical Society.

All three types can be explained by the following general scheme. The first step is a reversible interaction between the nitrite ion (nitrous acid) and another reactant (X), leading to the formation of a more reactive species which is then oxidized or reduced by R :

Based on the stationarity condition for N(III)Z, the rate is given by the following equation :

$$v = \frac{k_1[\text{N(III)}][\text{X}][\text{R}]}{k_{-1}[\text{Y}] + k_2[\text{R}]} \quad (3)$$

Depending on the relative value of the two terms in the denominator, the order for the oxidizing (reducing) agent is

$$0 \quad \text{if} \quad k_2[\text{R}] \gg k_{-1}[\text{Y}] ;$$

$$1 \quad \text{if} \quad k_2[\text{R}] \ll k_{-1}[\text{Y}]$$

with values between 0 and 1 if the two terms are comparable. Obviously, either of the two limiting rate equations can be valid only in a certain concentration range. Our measurements show that although the rate of oxidation of nitrous acid by permanganate is independent of the permanganate concentration

in a broad range of permanganate and nitrous acid concentrations, the permanganate influences the rate outside this concentration range (Fig. 1).

The peculiar form of the rate equation is responsible for the apparently controversial results of different authors, who obtained their rate equations under different concentration conditions.

Fig. 1 Rate of the nitrite—permanganate reaction as a function of permanganate concentration. For the leftside scale :

xxx $c_{\text{N}} = 0.834 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 2.63$
 000 $c_{\text{N}} = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $c_{\text{H}} = 1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$;

I = 0.5 ; for the rightside scale :

□□□ $c_{\text{N}} = 1.23 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-2}$, $c_{\text{H}} = 0.102 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$;

△△△ $c_{\text{N}} = 4.33 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $c_{\text{H}} = 9.91 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

In the rate equations listed in Tables 1-3 the concentration of hydrogen ion always occurs. The reason is that the nitrite ion takes part in different protonation equilibria :

TABLE 1. REACTIONS OF ZEROth ORDER FOR THE REACTANT

Reactant	Rate law	Important nitrogen-containing species	References
Mn(VII)	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2] + k_2[\text{HNO}_2]^2$ **	NO^+ N_2O_3	**
H_2O_2	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+]$	NO^-	3
SCN^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+][\text{NO}_2^-]$	N_2O_4	4
N_3^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+]$	NO^+	5
	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2$	N_2O_3	6
Mo(V)	$k[\text{HNO}_2]$	NO^+	3
$(\text{SO}_3)_2\text{NO}^{2-}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2$	N_2O_3	8
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2$	N_2O_3	9
	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+][\text{I}^-]$	NOI	9
	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+][\text{Br}^-]$	NOBr	9
	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{acetate}]$	NOAc	9

* Rate law at low nitrite concentration.

** Our result.

TABLE 2. REACTIONS OF FIRST ORDER FOR THE REACTANT

Reactant	Rate law	Important nitrogen-containing species	References
Fe(II)	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2][\text{Fe(II)}] + k_2[\text{HNO}_2][\text{Fe(II)}][\text{H}^+] + \frac{k_3}{p_{\text{NO}}}[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{Fe(II)}]$	$\text{NO}^+, \text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	10
Eu(II)	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2][\text{Eu(II)}][\text{NO}]$	$\text{H}_2\text{NO}_2, \text{NO}, \text{HNO}$	11
$\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{complex}][\text{H}^+]$	$\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NON}_3^{3+}$	12
$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{N}_3^{2+}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{complex}][\text{H}^+]$	$\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{NON}_3^{3+}$	13
$\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3^+$	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{complex}][\text{H}^+]$	$\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NON}_3^{3+}$	14
N_3^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{N}_3^-]$	$\text{N}_2\text{O}_3, \text{NON}_3$	6
	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{HN}_3][\text{H}^+]$	H_2NO_2^+	6
	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{N}_3^-][\text{H}^+]$	H_2NO_2^+	6
I^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{I}^-][\text{H}^+]$	NOI	15
SCN^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{SCN}^-][\text{H}^+][\text{NO}_3^-]$	N_2O_4	4
N_2H_4	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{N}_2\text{H}_4][\text{H}^+]$	$\text{NO}^+, \text{HNO}, \text{N}_2\text{H}_4$	16
	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{N}_2\text{H}_4][\text{H}]^2$	NO^+, HNO	17
RNH_2	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{RNH}_2]$	N_2O_3	9
HCOO^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{HCOO}^-][\text{H}^+]$	NO^+	10
$\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{CO}_4^{2-}][\text{H}^+]$	NO^+	10
$\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H}]$	$\text{H}_2\text{NO}_2^+, \text{ONNHSO}_3\text{H}$ $(\text{NH}_2\text{SO}_3\text{H} \dots \text{ONOH})$	18 17
Mn(III)	$\frac{k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2}{[\text{H}^+] + k_3} [\text{HNO}_2][\text{Mn(III)}]$	NO_2	19
Co(III)	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2][\text{Co(III)}] + k_2[\text{Co(III)}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}[\text{HNO}_2]$	NO_2	20
Ce(IV)	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{Ce(IV)}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}$	NO_2	**
H_2O_2	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}_2\text{O}_2][\text{H}^+] + k_3[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$	$\text{NO}^+, \text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	21
	$k[\text{NO}_2^-][\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]$		22
$\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_3\text{H}$	$k[\text{NO}_2^-][\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_3\text{H}]$		22
HSO_5^-	$k[\text{NO}_2^-][\text{HSO}_5^-]$		22
ClO_3^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{ClO}_3^-][\text{H}^+]$	NO^+	23
BrO_3^-	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{BrO}_3^-][\text{H}^+]$	NO^+	23
$\text{Co}_2(\text{NH}_3)_{10}\text{O}_2^{5+}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{complex}][\text{H}^+]^{-1}$	$\left\{ \text{Co}_2(\text{NH}_3)_{10}\text{O}_2^{5+}, \text{NO}_2 \right\}$	24

** Our result.

TABLE 3. MISCELLANEOUS REACTIONS

Reactant	Rate law	Important nitrogen-containing species	References
SO_3^{2-}	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{HNO}_2][\text{SO}_3^{2-}][\text{H}^+]$	NO^+	10
$\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$	$k[\text{HNO}_2][\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]^{0,2}[\text{H}^+]$		25
U(IV)	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2]^{0,5-0,1}[\text{U(IV)}][\text{H}^+]^{1,2,6}$		26
HONH ₂	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2]^{1,2} + \frac{k_2[\text{HNO}_2][\text{HONH}_2][\text{H}^+]}{k_4 + k_6[\text{H}^+]}$	$\text{H}_2\text{NO}_2^+, \text{ONNH}_2\text{OH}$	27
I^-	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{I}^-]^2[\text{H}^+]^2$		28
	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2][\text{I}^-]^2[\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{I}^-]^2[\text{H}^+]^2$	NOI, $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{I}^+$	**
Cr(VI)	$\frac{[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{Cr(VI)}](k_1 + k_2[\text{H}^+] + k_3[\text{Cr(VI)}])}{1 + k_4[\text{HNO}_2] + k_5[\text{HNO}_2]^2}$	CrO_3ONO^- , $\text{CrO}_7\text{N}_2\text{H}^-$	29**
	$\frac{k_2[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{Mn(VII)}]}{k_3[\text{Mn(VI)}] + k_4[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+]}$	$\text{MnO}_3\text{ONO}, \text{NO}^+$, N_2O_3	**
Mn(VII)	$k_1[\text{HNO}_2] + \frac{k_3[\text{Mn(VI)}] + k_4[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+]}{1 + k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]}$		
H_2O_2	$\frac{k_1[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}_2\text{O}_2][\text{H}^+]}{1 + k_2[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]}$	$\text{NO}^+, \text{HOONO}$	30

** Our result.

The N(III) in Eq. (1) may be either nitrous acid or nitrite acidium ion, their concentrations being determined by the above equilibria. Protonation and dehydration equilibria result in the highly reactive nitrosyl cation

Dimerization, that is isopolyacid formation, may also play an important role in the kinetics and mechanism of the redox reactions of N(III). Writing HNO_2 for X and H_2O for Y in Eq. (1)

the rates of the two limiting cases are

$$v = k[\text{HNO}_2]^2$$

and

$$v = k[\text{HNO}_2]^2[\text{R}]$$

Examples of both cases can be found in the Tables.

With halide ions N(III) forms reactive compounds such as NOI, NOBr and NOCl. This reaction is responsible for the appearance of the concentration of halide ion in some rate equations. An analogous reaction is the source of the effect of nitrate ion on the rates of redox reactions of N(III). The active species is dinitrogen tetroxide, which can be formulated as NONO_3 , some of its reaction indeed reflecting this structure.

There is also a possibility of the formation of reactive species in the presence of buffers (HB) :

The product either reacts directly in a redox reaction, or contributes through the following equilibrium :

to the increase of the N_2O_3 concentration. These reactions explain the rate-enhancing effect of acetate and phthalate in the diazotization reaction, and that of glycine in the permanganate—nitrite reaction (Fig. 2).

In the reduction with iodide the citrate—phosphate buffer caused a five-fold increase in the specific rate

($k_2 = 3.7 \times 10^{10} \text{ mol}^{-5} \text{ dm}^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$; and in presence a definite concentration of buffer : $k_2^B = 1.9 \times 10^{11} \text{ mol}^{-5} \text{ dm}^{15} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°).

Fig. 2. Rate of the nitrite-permanganate reaction as a function of glycine concentration. $c_N = 3.06 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{KMnO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $\text{pH} = 1.63$.

Equilibria involving N(III) may lead to the formation of species of diminished reactivity. This is the case in the last three reactions of Table 3. The peculiar dependence of the rate of the chromium(VI)—nitrite reaction on the total concentration of nitrite (Fig. 3) means that the concentration of nitrogen(III) must also occur in the denominator of the rate equation.

Fig. 3. Variation of rate of Cr(VI)—nitrite reaction with c_N . $[\text{H}^+] = 0.137 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cr(VI)}] = 9.312 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $I = 0.5$. The plotted points are those measured, and the curve is the calculated function :

$$v = \frac{2.30 \times 10^{-3} c_N^2}{1 + 10.2 c_N + 300 c_N^2}$$

We therefore assumed the following rapid equilibria leading to the formation of heteropolyacids :

The given values of the equilibrium constants were obtained from the kinetic measurements. The relatively high stability of the second complex could be explained by the ring structure. However, analysis of the data permits the postulation of only the composition and not the structure of the species.

These equilibria lead to the decrease of the concentration of HCrO_4^- . From analysis of the data it follows that in effect only the second complex undergoes a redox change.

The situation is similar in the permanganate oxidation and the stability constant of the species MnO_3ONO could be determined from the rate data.

The effects of different substances on the iodide—nitrite reaction are due to the formation of nitrogen(III)—containing species of different reactivities. The fact that the first-order reaction for the nitrite is not influenced by citrate—phosphate buffer, while the second-order reaction is greatly enhanced by this buffer, indicates that another species takes part in the second-order pathway. This is the basis of our assumption that, besides NOI , the species $\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{I}^+$ also plays a role in the mechanism. This assumption is supported by the observed inhibitory effect of bromide ions.

Depending on the properties of the reactant, other types of pre-equilibria may occur. In the oxidation by cerium(IV) the dependence of the rate on the hydrogen ion concentration requires the assumption of the formation of a hydroxo complex. Hydroxo complexes are also probably involved in the oxidations by cobalt(III) and manganese(III). The rate vs. cerium(IV) concentration curve seems to indicate that polynuclear complex formation too must be considered: the order for cerium(IV) exceeds one. (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Rate of the cerium(IV)—nitrite reaction as a function of cerium(IV) concentration. $c_N = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $\text{pH} = 1.99$.

The greater reactivity of hydroxocomplexes can be explained by the following hydrogen-bridge for-

ming interaction $\text{M}-\overset{\text{H}}{\text{O}} \cdots \text{H}-\text{O}-\text{N}=\text{O}$ which is followed by hydrogen atom transfer. Hydrogen bridges are certainly involved in other interactions too. For example in the reaction of sulphamic acid with nitrous acid the formation of the following species was assumed.

The most likely reason for the second-order dependence of the rate of the reaction between nitrite and $\text{Co}_2(\text{NH}_3)_8\text{O}_2^{5+}$ on the nitrite concentration is the formation of an outer sphere complex $\text{Co}_2(\text{NH}_3)_8^-\text{O}_2, \text{NO}_2^{4+}$. The reaction of this complex with another nitrite ion results in the redox change.

The aforementioned reactions are of importance in the mechanisms reflected in the empirical rate laws because there are fairly big differences in the reactivities of the nitrogen(III)-containing species. Although

it is not always possible to calculate exactly the rate constants of the different routes, an approximate calculation indicates that these differences can sometimes be quite dramatic. This is illustrated by the data of Table 4 where the rate constant of the following reaction

is shown for a few N(III)-containing species.

TABLE 4

Species	k_2 $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
NO_2^-	$> 10^{-2}$
MnO_3ONO	$> 10^{-1*}$
HNO_2	$> 10^0$
MNO_3ONO	$> 10^2$
N_2O_3	$\sim 10^8$
NO^+	$\sim 10^{10}$

*This value is the rate constant of the intramolecular electron transfer reaction.

These data clearly demonstrate how greatly the reactivity of a certain atom is influenced by its immediate environment. Another important, but less trivial conclusion is that in certain cases the intramolecular electron transfer may be more hindered than the redox reaction in a bimolecular step. This is indicated by the comparison of the two rate constants referring to the species MnO_3ONO .

Reactions of coordinatively bound nitrogen(III)

Nitrogen(III) in an ideal species on which to study the effect of coordination on reactivity. There are a number of metal complexes containing N(III). Some complexes of different types are listed in Table 5.

It can be assumed that the reactivity of the coordinated N(III) species is influenced by the following factors :

- (i) the basic form of the coordinated ligand (NO_2^- , NO^+) ;
- (ii) the donor atom (N or O, or both) ;
- (iii) properties of the complex core :
 - (a) electron structures of the metal center and of the core, that is the effect of the other coordinated ligands on the electron distribution,
 - (b) stereochemistry of the complex (packing, relative positions of the ligands, etc.).

It appears possible to find model compounds to studying these effects. We are now systematically investigating this family of complexes. Unfortunately, we cannot offer detailed mechanisms of these reactions in this survey, but comparison of the different reactions permits some worthwhile conclusions.

Experiments with the labile mercury(II) and zinc(II) complexes show that coordination to these metal ions strongly decreases the reactivity of nitrite towards either permanganate or iodide ; that is, a great decrease of rate was observed on the effect of these metal ions. The retardation is so considerable that the contribution of the reaction of the coordinated nitrite to the total reaction is too small to be measured. These experiments permit the estimation of an approximate stability constant for HgNO_2^+ , and it is clear that the earlier published value is smaller than the real one by two orders of magnitude.

In the case of the nitrite—iodide reaction the earlier experiments claimed that zinc(II) ions enhance the reaction. We found, however, that this

TABLE 5. TYPES OF NITROGEN(III)-CONTAINING COMPLEXES

Labile Complexes*	Inert complexes		
	Nitrito complexes	Nitro complexes	Nitrosyl complexes
$[\text{ZnNO}_2]^+$	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{ONO}]^{2+}$	$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_{6-n}(\text{NO}_2)_n]^{2-n}$	$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]^+$
$[\text{CdNO}_2]^+$	$[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{ONO}]^{2+}$	$[\text{Rh}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]^{2+}$	$[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}]^{2+}$
$[\text{HgNO}_2]^+$	$[\text{Ir}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{ONO}]^{2+}$	$[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]^{2+}$	$[\text{Ru}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]^{2-}$
	$[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{ONO}]^{2+}$	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]^{2+}$	$[\text{Ru}(\text{SCN})_5\text{NO}]^{2-}$
		cis- and trans- $[\text{Coen}_2\text{ClNO}_2]^+$	
		$[\text{Coen}_2\text{NH}_3\text{NO}_2]^{2+}$	

*Ratio of the nitro and nitrito forms in the equilibrium mixture is not known.

increase is due to the increase of the hydrogen ion concentration caused by the hydrolysis of the zinc(II) ions. With the pH of the reaction mixture constant, a decrease of the rate could be observed. The recent findings of Indelli et al. on the rate-decreasing effect of thorium(IV) ions in the same reaction also indicate the formation of less reactive complexes.

Most reactions of the nitro group in the inert nitropentaamminecobalt(III) complex are so slow that they cannot be studied because of the different side-reactions (slow decomposition of the complex or of the reactants, etc.). In the case of the isomeric nitrito compound the reactions are faster, but simultaneous aquation and isomerization again make exact rate studies impossible. Both complexes exhibit an interesting reaction with azide ion. The interaction of the nitro group and the azide ion is indicated by the change of the spectrum of the reaction mixture with time, but no gas evolution is observed.

Fig. 5. Change of spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{NO}_2]\text{Cl}_2$ on effect of NaN_3
 (a) spectrum of the 1.25×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} (4 cm cell)
 (b) complex + 0.5 mole cm^{-3} NaN_3 (after 20 min)

Under the same conditions—in neutral medium—there is no reaction between nitrite and azide ions, while in acidic solutions gaseous products are formed according to the following reaction

The reaction of the complex with azide is reversible. By the slow evaporation of the solvent a solid crystalline product was obtained. We hope that information will be provided by the infrared studies now in progress. It is assumed that the product contains a coordinated nitrosyl azide. The free compound was prepared earlier³⁰; it is fairly unstable, but it is not unreasonable to assume that coordination can stabilize it.

It is interesting to compare the reaction of the nitro complex and azide ion with that of the analogous azido complex with nitrite. According to Haim and Taube, coordinated nitrosyl azide is formed in this reaction, although this cannot be detected because of the fast decomposition :

The reaction studied by us may be termed the inverse reaction and leads to a stable product

This comparison indicates the dramatic difference in the reaction depending on which of the reactants is coordinated.

The most interesting observations were made in the reactions of the nitrosylpentacyanoiron(II) complex. Most of the reactions are much slower than those of the nitrite ion. This decrease of reactivity is particularly striking, considering the high reactivity of the free nitrosyl ion. However, the reactions of this complex with ammonia and its derivatives are much faster than the analogous reactions of the free nitrite ion. Under the same conditions, the reaction of hydroxylamine with the complex

is twenty times faster than the corresponding reaction with nitrite. A change of the spectrum is found after the evolution of N_2O . These observations and the analysis of the rate data suggest the following mechanism :

III can be obtained by the reaction of hydroxylamine with the aquopentacyanoiron(II) complex. There is indirect evidence for the formation of II. It is expected that II should be a more powerful nitrosating agent than the original complex. Consequently it

should react rapidly with other agents capable of nitrosation. In accordance with this speculation no reaction was observed on mixing nitrosylpentacyano-iron(II) and sulphanilic acid, while a fast increase of absorbancy was observed on adding hydroxylamine to this mixture. (Hydroxylamine alone does not react with sulphanilic acid.)

The reactions of nitroprussiate with hydrazine and phenylhydrazine are also much faster than those of the free ligand. However, this reaction is very complicated, as indicated by the following facts :

- (i) According to the mass spectrometric analysis four gaseous products (N₂O, N₂, NO, NH₃) are formed besides other products.
- (ii) The reaction occurs in the dark, but a strong effect of illumination was observed.
- (iii) If the volume of evolved gases is plotted vs. time the curve is monotonous only in the absence of oxygen ; in the presence of oxygen the curve exhibits two extrema.

Fig. 6. The volume of gases evolved as a function of time in the reaction of Na₂[Fe(CN)₅NO] and hydrazine. [complex]=4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [N₂H₄.H₂O]=1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ ; pH=9.3 ; xxx in a nitrogen atmosphere ; 000 in the presence of air, Δ Δ Δ in an oxygen atmosphere.

These overshoot—undershoot curves are of theoretical importance and can be explained by the following mechanism. Besides the primarily formed N₂O, a relatively long-living intermediate complex is formed which can react with oxygen.

This can then release some gaseous product :

By this simple mechanism the experimentally found curves could be well calculated. Nevertheless, some other reactions also occur in the system : this scheme cannot account for the formation of NO.

The nitrosyl complex reacts rapidly with ammonia too :

The analogous reaction or the thermal decomposition of ammonium nitrite is infinitely slow under the same conditions. (This latter reaction occurs in concentrated solution at 100°). The spectrophotometric measurements indicate the formation of two intermediates. One of these could be identified by comparative experiments as Fe(CN)₅NO₂H³⁻, and there is some evidence that the other is a dinitrogen complex formed in the following reaction :

Unfortunately, it is practically impossible to get direct evidence for the formation of this species. We could obtain a precipitate from the reaction mixture by adding a solution of Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃. It was expected that the complex ion with charge plus three would form a precipitate with that with charge minus three. The precipitates obtained at different reaction times were heated at 100°, and the evolved gases were analysed mass-spectrometrically. The results are given in Table 6.

TABLE 6. COMPOSITION OF GASEOUS PRODUCTS EVOLVED BY HEATING PRECIPITATE OBTAINED FROM A REACTION MIXTURE OF NITROSYL PENTACYANO FERRATE(II) AND AMMONIA (DATA ARE IN v/v%).

Gas	0.5 min	1 min	2 min	25 min	60 min
NH ₃	80.1	88.0	90.9	94.4	94.2
N ₂	14.3	9.4	7.4	4.1	3.9
NO	0.9	0.7	1.0	0.9	0.6
N ₂ O	4.6	1.9	0.7	0.6	1.5

It was found in separate experiments that none of the compounds known to be involved in the reaction undergo individual thermal decomposition to give

nitrogen under the given conditions, and nitrogen evolution is therefore due to the decomposition of the intermediate. Infrared studies do not give useful evidence because the very intense $C \equiv N$ bands mask the weak $N \equiv N$ band.

These studies raised a novel possibility of biological nitrogen fixation. In principle there are three ways for this :

- (i) reduction,
- (ii) oxidation,
- (iii) disproportionation, that is heterolytic splitting.

This is the reverse of the reaction between ammonia and the nitrite ion.

The first two possibilities are usually considered and model experiments are directed towards these types of reactions only. The reason is obvious : the heterolytic splitting of the dinitrogen molecule is thermodynamically extremely unfavourable. Based on the available data the enthalpy change of the reaction

is about +2000 (!) kcal mol⁻¹. However, there is a dramatic drop in the energy necessary for this heterolytic splitting when the reaction occurs in aqueous solution : The enthalpy of the following reaction

is only +70 kcal mol⁻¹. The role of complex formation can be two-fold. The coordination of the products of the disproportionation reaction can contribute to make the reaction thermodynamically more favourable. An even more important consequence can be the decrease of the kinetic barrier. This is more important because a not very endothermic reaction may occur at the expense of some coupled exothermic processes. There are many examples of such reactions under biological conditions. Our experience with the nitrosyl complexes seems to

indicate that further work in this direction may be rewarding.

References

1. J. B. RAYNOR, *Inorg. Chim. Acta.*, 1972, 6, 347.
2. L. CAMBI and L. SZEGO, *Atti. Acad. Nazi Lincei*, 1927, 5, 737. J. H. SWINEHART, *Coordin. Chem. Rev.* 1964, 2, 385.
3. M. ANBAR and H. TAUBE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 6243
4. M. N. HUGHES, E. D. PHILIPS, G. STEDMAN and P.A.E. WEINCUP, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A) 1969, 1148.
5. F. SEEL and R. SCHWAEBE, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1953, 274, 169.
6. G. STEDMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1702.
7. J. A. FRANK and J. T. SPENCE, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1964, 68, 2131.
8. J. C. M. LI and D. M. RITTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3024, 5823.
9. J. H. RIDD, *Quart. Rev.* 1961, 15, 418.
10. T. A. TURNEY and G. A. WRIGHT, *Chem. Rev.* 1959, 59, 497.
11. R. T. M. FRASER, R. N. LEE and K. HAYDEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1967, 741.
12. A. HAIM and H. TAUBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 1199.
13. T.C. MATTS and P. MOORE, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 2819.
14. C. S. DAVIS and G. C. LALOR, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)* 1968, 1095.
15. M. BOBTELSKY, and D. KAPLAN, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1930, 189, 234
16. V. SZ. KOLTUNOV and V. I. MARCSENKO, *Kinetika i Kataliz* 1966, 7, 224 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 65, 3060 e.
17. P. BIDDLE and J. H. Miles, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1291.
18. M. N. HUGHES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A) 1967, 902.
19. G. DAVIES and K. KUSTIN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 484.
20. G. DAVIES and K. O. WATKINS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 74, 3388.
21. E. A. SILOV and Z. SZ. SZTYEPANOVA, *Zs. Fiz. Him.*, 1950, 24, 800.
22. J. O. EDWARDS and J. J. MUELLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 696.
23. W. G. LOWE and D. J. BROWNE, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1934, 221, 173 ; *Chem Abst.*, 1935, 5337^b
24. M. GREEN and A. G. SYKES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A) 1970, 3209.
25. J. O. EDWARDS, *Science*, 1951, 113, 392.
26. V. SZ. KOLTUNOV, *Himija transzuranovih elementov, Akademia Nauk SzSzsZr. Otd. Obs. Tech. Him.* 1967, 8-17 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, 70, 23364.
27. G. STEDMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1963, 2824.
28. F. FERRANTI, A. INDELLI, F. SECCO and M. G. LUCARELLI, *Gazetta Chimica Italiana*, 1972, 102, 125.
29. D. A. DURHAM, L. DOZSA and M. T. BECK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 2971.
30. D. J. BENTON and P. MOORE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1970, 3179
31. H. W. LUCIEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 4458.